

UDC 343.23:324.77/.78

Sadih Rza ohly Tahiev –

*Doctor of Sciences (Law), Associate Professor,
Honored Lawyer of Ukraine,
Head of the Department of Criminal,
Criminal and Executive Law and Criminology of the
Penitentiary Academy of Ukraine
(34 Honcha Street, Chernihiv, 14000, Ukraine)
ORCID: 0000-0001-9338-4792*

Yana M. Krupko –

*candidate of juridical sciences, associate professor,
Head of the PhD and
Doctoral Program,
Penitentiary Academy of Ukraine
(34 Honcha Street, Chernihiv, 14000, Ukraine)
ORCID: 0000-0002-1578-2303*

Peculiarities of Aggravating Circumstances Application– Committing a Crime under Conditions of Martial Law or State of Emergency, other Emergency Situations

Стаття присвячена дослідженню застосування обставин, що обтяжують покарання-вчинення злочину з використанням умов воєнного або надзвичайного стану, інших надзвичайних подій. Після повномасштабного вторгнення російської федерації на територію України та введення в державі правового режиму воєнного стану законодавцем посилено кримінальну відповідальність за низку злочинів, вчинених в особливий період.

З'ясовано, що аналіз обвинувальних вироків не дає змоги визначити, яким чином відбувається відповідне врахування обставин, що пом'якшують і обтяжують покарання, при призначенні покарання.

Саме тому у статті порушуються питання про необхідність нормативного визначення чітких правил врахування відповідних обставин у призначеному покаранні. На прикладі судової практики були визначені особливості застосування обставин, що обтяжують покарання - це вчинення злочину з використанням умов воєнного або надзвичайного стану, інших надзвичайних подій.

Ключові слова: *воєнний стан, надзвичайний стан, обставини, що пом'якшують покарання, обставини, що обтяжують покарання, кримінальна відповідальність, судова практика, кваліфікація кримінальних правопорушень, призначення покарання, індивідуалізація, злочини проти власності, Верховний Суд.*

Having made the analyses of the criminal proceedings, we found out that the aggravating circumstances in the court decision were cited in wording that did not comply with Article 67 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, and a number of aggravating circumstances are described in the law in a generalized, standard form.

The analysis of the guilty decisions does not allow us to determine how the mitigating and aggravating circumstances are taken into account when sentencing. However, when taking into account the mitigating circumstances, one can guess when a judge, in the presence of one or more such circumstances and in the absence of aggravating circumstances, sentences a person to the minimum punishment provided for by the sanction of the article. However, it is currently impossible to establish how such consideration is made in the case of simultaneous presence of mitigating and aggravating circumstances, since the judge only refers to them in the court decision without making an appropriate analysis.

After the full-scale invasion of Ukraine by the russian federation and the introduction of martial law in the country, the legislator increased criminal liability for a number of crimes committed during the special period.

That is why the article raises the issue of the need for regulatory definition of clear rules for taking into account the relevant circumstances in the sentence imposed. For the instance of judicial practice, the peculiarities of application of aggravating circumstances were defined, such as the commission of a crime using the conditions of martial law or a state of emergency, or other emergency situations. This article will provide an opportunity to develop reasonable recommendations for improving the norms of the law on criminal liability in the researched area and clarifying their application by law enforcement personnel and courts in practice.

In the theory of criminal law, considerable attention is paid to the circumstances mitigating and aggravating punishment, which indicates their important criminal law significance. However, a significant number of important aspects of taking into account the circumstances mitigating and aggravating punishment in the course of qualification of criminal offenses and sentencing for their commission are not fully covered and studied in the theory of criminal law.

Keywords: *martial law, state of emergency, circumstances mitigating punishment, circumstances aggravating punishment, criminal liability, judicial practice, qualification of criminal offenses, sentencing, individualization, crimes against property, Supreme Court.*

Target setting. Circumstances that mitigate and aggravate punishment, first of all, are the basis for imposing a more severe or less severe punishment and are subject to establish and consider at the sentencing hearing.

The results of the court practice analysis make it possible to assert that judges take a predominantly formal approach to fulfilling the legal requirement to take into account mitigating or aggravating circumstances when imposing a sentence. This is also confirmed by the results of the study and analysis of court practice, which will be further discussed in this article.

The analysis of the guilty verdicts does not allow us to determine how the mitigating and aggravating circumstances are taken into account when imposing a sentence. However, when considering the mitigating circumstances, one can guess when a judge, in the presence of one or more such circumstances and in the absence of aggravating circumstances, sentences a person to the minimum punishment provided for by the sanction of the article. However, it is currently impossible to establish how such consideration is made in the case of simultaneous presence of mitigating and aggravating circumstances, since the judge only refers to them in the court decision without making an appropriate analysis.

That is why we raise the issue of the need for regulatory definition of clear rules of accounting the relevant circumstances in the sentence imposed. Given this rather unclear approach to legislative regulation of the procedure of taking into account the circumstances mitigating and aggravating punishment, this issue is receiving considerable attention in

the science of criminal law, justifying various ways to improve legislation in this area.

The consideration of circumstances mitigating and aggravating punishment depends on the practice of application and the state of legislative regulation of this process. A proper legal assessment of the circumstances that characterize the externally negative socially dangerous act or the person who committed it is important to ensure a proper legal assessment of the criminal offense. Undoubtedly, it is as in all other processes related to bringing a person to criminal liability.

That is why criminal law contains norms that regulate certain aspects related to the circumstances mitigating and aggravating punishment, namely: the existence of a separate determined article (Article 66 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine) [1]. This article defines the list of circumstances mitigating the punishment, indicating that it is mandatory for the court and that it is non-exhaustive; the existence of a separate article (Article 67 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine), which defines the list of circumstances aggravating the punishment, indicating that it is exhaustive; the existence of a separate article (Article 69 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine), which stipulates that the combination of relevant circumstances, if any, may result in a lighter sentence than provided by law; the existence of a separate article (Article 69–1 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine), which sets the upper limit of the sentence that may be imposed on a person in the presence of a combination of specific mitigating circumstances and other conditions set in this article.

The purpose of the article. This article will provide an opportunity to develop reasonable recommendations for improving the norms of the law on

criminal liability in the researched area and clarifying their application by law enforcement personnel and courts in practice.

Analyses of research and publications. In the theory of criminal law, considerable attention is paid to the circumstances mitigating and aggravating punishment, which indicates their important criminal law significance. The study of issues related to the circumstances mitigating and aggravating punishment has been widely searched in the science of criminal law, in particular in the context of works related to the peculiarities of sentencing. This includes the scientific works of V.V. Poltavets, T.V. Sakharuk, M.O. Skriabin, V.I. Tkachenko, L.M. Fedorak, I.M. Fedorchuk, P.L. Fris, and B.O. Chuprynskyi. However, a significant number of important aspects of taking into account the circumstances mitigating and aggravating punishment in the course of qualification of criminal offenses and sentencing for their commission are not fully covered and studied in the theory of criminal law.

The statement of basic materials. Moreover, regarding the large-scale invasion of Ukraine by the Russian armed forces, by the Presidential Decree of February 24, 2022, No. 64/2022, martial law in Ukraine was introduced, which contained measures necessary to ensure the defense of Ukraine, protect the security of the population and the interests of the state [2].

After the full-scale invasion in Ukraine by the Russian Federation and the introduction of martial law in the country, the legislator increased criminal liability for a number of crimes committed during the special period.

Despite the established judicial practice, the Board of Judges of the First Trial Chamber of the Criminal Cassation Court of the Supreme Court, considering case No. 722/594/22 [3], questioned the correctness of the qualification of the Appellate Court of actions under Part 4 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine on the qualifying ground of “committing a crime under conditions of martial law”, perceived it as leading to a violation of the principle of individualization of punishment. Due to the need to deviate from the legal positions expressed in the practice of the Criminal Cassation Court regarding the application of Part 4 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine under the qualifying ground of “committing a crime under conditions of martial law or a state of emergency”, the case was referred to the Grand Chamber of the Supreme Court for its

consideration. The Grand Chamber of the Supreme Court by its decision of May 25, 2023, returned the proceedings for further consideration to the First Trial Chamber of the Criminal Cassation Court, finding no exceptional legal problem, no need to deviate from previous conclusions and from the practice established by the court. Subsequently, the proceedings were transferred to the Joint Chamber of the Criminal Cassation Court of the Supreme Court, based on the need to ensure compliance with the principle of legal certainty. The Joint Chamber of the Criminal Cassation Court established the statutory grounds for cassation review of this proceeding.

In this criminal proceeding, the Chernivtsi Appeal Court sentenced the defendant to imprisonment on July 14, 2022 under Part 3 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine for a term of 3 years, under Part 4 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine for a term of 5 years, and for the aggregate of crimes under Article 70 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine for a final term of 5 years. The crimes were committed on February 08, 2022, March 08, 2022 and March 09, 2022.

By the Resolution of the Cassation Court on January 15, 2024, the court decision was left unchanged.

The Cassation Court came to the conclusion that when qualifying property crimes, in particular theft, under the qualifying ground of “committing a crime under conditions of martial law”, the following should be taken into account.

By the Law of Ukraine of March 03, 2022 No. 2117-IX “On Amendments to the Criminal Code of Ukraine on Strengthening Liability for Looting” [4] were amended Parts 4 of Articles 185 – 187, 189 and 191 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine and supplemented with a qualifying feature for committing crimes “under conditions of martial law or a state of emergency”.

As a result of these changes, theft under conditions of martial law after the entry into force of the Law (dated March 07, 2022), regardless of the circumstances of the crime and other qualifying features (repetition, prior conspiracy, penetration, large size, etc.), should be qualified under Part 4 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine.

At the same time, among the aggravating circumstances, the criminal law provides for “committing a crime under conditions of martial law or a state of emergency, other emergency situations” (Clause

11, Part 1, Article 67 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine).

It should be emphasized that the similarity of the wording used as a qualifying feature of a number of crimes (committed under conditions of martial law or a state of emergency) and as an aggravating circumstance (committed using the conditions of martial law or a state of emergency) should not lead to misinterpretation and application of the law on criminal liability in practice.

In addition to the above practice, the Criminal Cassation Court expressed its legal position on the assessment of theft committed under conditions of martial law (Part 4 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine) in its decision of January 17, 2023 in case No. 404/3367/22 and noted that the qualifying feature “committing a crime under conditions of martial law” is not identical to the circumstances of committing a crime using martial law. A similar position is contained in the resolutions of November 23, 2022 (case No. 466/1973/22), December 05, 2022 (case No. 175/965/22), July 31, 2023 (case No. 369/9491/22), August 08, 2023 (case No. 759/1736/23), September 01, 2023 (case No. 643/2261/23), September 08, 2023 (case No. 725/585/23), as well as in resolutions of March 02, 2023 (case No. 477/378/22) and of August 30, 2023 (case No. 629/1724/22), in which the Criminal Cassation Court, reviewing court decisions against persons convicted of various crimes, did not question the correctness of the qualification of the guilty actions under the qualifying ground “committing a crime under conditions of martial law” [3].

It should be noted that this qualifying feature does not contain an indication of the specific territory of the crime. The very fact that the legal regime of martial law was introduced throughout Ukraine necessitates the qualification of a number of property crimes (Articles 185 – 187, 189 and 191 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine) under Part 4 of the relevant articles.

During the cassation review of case No. 722/594/22, the court concluded that the provision of the law of Ukraine on criminal liability under Part 4 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine is applicable in the case of “committing a criminal offense under conditions of martial law or a state of emergency”, and “committing a crime under conditions of martial law” (Clause 11, Part 1, Article 67 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine) as an aggravating

circumstance may be taken into account by the court only in terms of individualizing criminal liability.

The Joint Chamber of the Criminal Cassation Court disagreed with the arguments of the Board of Judges of the First Trial Chamber of the Criminal Cassation Court regarding the severity of the punishment established in the sanction of the criminal law provision for committing an act containing a particularly qualified form of theft (under martial law). In addition, the resolution emphasizes the unreasonable identification by the Board of Judges of the differentiation of criminal liability, the implementation of which belongs to the exclusive powers of the legislator, and its individualization by the court under the aggravating circumstance of “committing a crime under conditions of martial law” (Clause 11, Part 1, Article 67 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine). This, in the opinion of the Joint Chamber of the Criminal Cassation Court, is an interference with the exclusive competence of the legislator by derogating from the imperative provisions of the law and actually creating a new provision of the law on criminal liability that is beyond the powers of the court, and neutralizes the goal sought by the legislator under Law No. 2117-IX, setting out the disposition of Part 4 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine in the relevant edition. According to the above mentioned, the Supreme Court concluded that under Part 4 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, liability arises for committing a criminal offense under conditions of martial law or a state of emergency in the territory in which it was introduced. The full text of the decision of the Joint Chamber of the Criminal Court of Cassation within the Supreme Court of January 15, 2024 in case No. 722/594/22 is available in the Unified State Register of Court Decisions (hereinafter – USRCD) under the registration number 116446106 [3].

A similar position was expressed by the Supreme Court in its decision of January 18, 2024 in case No. 740/1586/23 [3].

Unequal interpretation by judges of the qualifying feature of criminal offenses “committed under conditions of martial law or a state of emergency” leads to different qualifications of similar crimes, which is an incorrect application of the law of Ukraine on criminal liability.

Thus, by the decision of the Criminal Cassation Court of the Supreme Court of January 31, 2024, the prosecutor’s cassation appeal cancelled the resolution of the Chernihiv Court of Appeal of June 14,

2023 regarding PERSON_1 under Part 3 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine and appointed a new appeal hearing.

According to the indictment, PERSON_1 was accused of being in the neighbourhood of the military camp № 17 in Pryluky city on February 07, 2023, in the conditions of martial law, acting repeatedly for mercenary motives, climbing over a low fence broke the glass of a wooden window and entered the apartment of the household, from where he / she secretly stole an electric tool and its components, causing the victim material damage in the total amount of 5080.36 UAH.

The court of first instance concluded that PERSON_1 was guilty of committing theft of other person's property, committed repeatedly, under conditions of martial law with breaking and entering, and qualified his actions under Part 4 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine.

Reviewing the judgement of the local court, the Appeal Court concluded that the actions of the accused lacked such a qualifying feature as committing a theft under conditions of martial law and reclassified the actions under Part 3 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine – theft committed repeatedly, with breaking and entering.

In justifying its decision, the Appellate Court noted that no military operations were conducted and are not currently being conducted in the city where the theft took place, all its residents live an ordinary life, and the accused did not use martial law conditions when committing the criminal offense.

However, the Cassation Court disagreed with such conclusions of the Appellate Court and upheld the arguments of the prosecutor's complaint about the unjustified reclassification of the convict's actions from Part 4 to Part 3 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, noting the following.

By the Law of Ukraine "On Amendments to the Criminal Code of Ukraine on Strengthening Liability for Looting" of March 03, 2022 [4], liability for criminal offenses under Articles 185, 186, 187, 189, 191 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine committed under conditions of martial law was increased, and the Law of Ukraine "On Amendments to the Criminal Code and the Criminal Procedure Code of Ukraine on Elimination of Contradictions in the Punishability of Criminal Offenses" of July 13, 2023 [5], under Article 190 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine committed under martial law.

According to mentioned amendments, theft committed under conditions of martial law or a state of emergency is qualified under Part 4 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, which provides for a sentence of imprisonment for a term of 5 to 8 years.

At the same time, the norm of the law of Ukraine on criminal liability provided for in Part 4 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine is applicable in the case of "committing a criminal offense under conditions of martial law or a state of emergency", and "committing a crime under conditions of martial law" (Clause 11 of Part 1 of Article 67 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine) as an aggravating circumstance may be taken into account by the court only in the aspect of individualization of criminal liability. According to Part 4 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, criminal liability is provided for the commission of a criminal offense under conditions of martial law or a state of emergency in the territory where it was introduced.

This position is consistent with the conclusion of the Joint Chamber of the Criminal Cassation Court of the Supreme Court (Resolution of January 15, 2024 in case No. 722/594/22).

Thus, Part 4 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine does not provide for such an interpretation and qualifying feature as committing theft using the conditions of martial law or committing it on a certain territory of Ukraine where military operations are taking place.

According to the factual circumstances established by the courts of previous instances, which were not disputed by the participants in the trial, the convict committed the theft on February 07, 2023, while staying in a neighbourhood of a military camp in Pryluky city, Chernihiv region, i.e. on the territory of Ukraine during martial law.

Thus, given the established circumstances, the Board of Judges agreed with the arguments of the prosecutor's cassation appeal that in this criminal proceeding, the Appeal Court, by reclassifying the actions of the convict from Part 4 to Part 3 of Article 185 of the Criminal Code of Ukraine, incorrectly applied the law of Ukraine on criminal liability.

The full text of the resolution is available in the USRCD under case No. 742/925/23.

Conclusions. In view of the above mentioned, in order to take measures aimed at ensuring unity in law application, it is necessary to take into account the above-mentioned circumstances when

conducting procedural guidance and supporting public prosecution in court.

References:

1. Criminal Code of Ukraine: Code of Ukraine dated 05.04.2005 № 2341-III. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2341-14#Text>.
2. On Introduction of Martial Law. Order of the President of Ukraine dated 24.02.2022 № 64/2022. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/64/2022#Text> (date of access 22.04.2024).
3. Unified State Register of Court Decisions. URL: <https://reyestr.court.gov.ua/>
4. On Amendments to the Criminal Code of Ukraine on Strengthening Liability for Looting. Law of Ukraine dated 03.03.2022 № 2117-IX. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/2117-20#Text> (date of access 22.04.2024).
5. On Amendments to the Criminal Code and the Criminal Procedure Code of Ukraine on Elimination of Contradictions in the Punishability of Criminal Offenses. Law of Ukraine dated 13.07.2023 № 3233-IX. URL: <https://zakon.rada.gov.ua/laws/show/3233-20#Text> (date of access 22.04.2024).
6. Scientific and Practical Commentary to the Criminal Code of Ukraine. 4th Ed., rev. and suppl./ Ed. by S.S. Iatsenko. K.: A.S.K., 2005. 848 p.